

THE TRENDS AND CHALLENGES OF INDIA'S AGRICULTURAL LABOURERS AMID LOCKDOWN-2020

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ABSTRACT

In India, the Majority of the Agricultural labourers and small farmers have faced the unbearable situation with regard to farming activities, scarce labour force for agricultural work, marketing of agricultural products, deterioration of demand for their agricultural products, the present fund constraints, even though re-investment in the field of agriculture work, the minimum availability of transport facilities only covered within the short distance say for example within the district, these are all surmounted problems raised due to with the sudden invent of COVID-19, as the consequences of two phases of lockdown in the 21 days and 14 days respectively.

During this period the on fourth of agricultural commodities are sold out, the remaining $\frac{3}{4}$ of agricultural production are not procured at the point of the stipulated period. Moreover, Agricultural commodity sellers are also faced the variety number of issues like more than 40Kms travelled by carrying commodity bags, the imprudence of police personnel and the end result from the meagre amount of earning income per day.

The less duration of marketing of agricultural products the early 50 per cent of products are wasted, because of agriculture commodities are perishable in nature. In this present paper mainly argues that how to solve agriculture labour problems, the labour shortage in the agricultural economy and

marketing of agriculture commodities with enough level of income. While at the normal course of the day as well as the present lockdown situation in India.

Keywords: *Net Domestic Product, Hunger free, Nationwide emergency, Micro level planning, Inter-linking of Rivers, Migrant labour force, Agriculture produce.*

INTRODUCTION

India's agriculture sector engaged by the 40 percent of the labour force, even though, it had earned only 16 percent of Gross Domestic product Apart from the normal course of days, like that the present two phases of lockdown situation from March 22nd, 2020 onwards to forthcoming May 03rd, 2020 with its effects India's Agricultural sector severely affected by ups and downs.

Growth Projection 2020 According to an IMF report on April 15, states that When compared to the corona virus-infected developed countries like U.S.A is minus -5.9 per cent. The United Kingdom is minus -6.5 per cent, whereas in Indian Economy growth rate is top amongst the World is Plus +1.9 per cent, the second place occupied by the china is plus +1.2 per cent and the third place occupied by Indonesia is plus +0.5 per cent, therefore, Indian Economy is still alive with a positive framework on the basis of Agriculture sector development, during the period of lockdown, because it is viable and reliable one among all the sectors. The other major sectors do not operate that lockdown really India's Agriculture sector as a stimulant factor the growth of the Economy standstill at the first rank in the midst COVID-19.

Indian Agriculture sector to feed the Industrial sector and the Industrial sector raw materials are used upon the Industrial sector. It is true that the Industrial sector and Agricultural sector both are interdependent. In the Midst of lockdown, the Agriculture sector provides the food supply to farm sector workers as well as Industrial sector workers. Here India's Agricultural sector would enhance the hunger-free India during this nationwide emergency. We appreciate for the National wide emergency event, on the other hand, Indian Agriculture faces the some of the notable problems like poor marketing of Agricultural goods, The complete absence of transport facility less expected demand, introduced by the police personnel at the marketing and sales, non-

availability of farmworkers as the consequences the increased wage level for Agricultural labourers . The present paper analyses the pros and cons of Indian Agriculture at the Impact of COVID-19 and also provide an effective strategic measure to sustain Indian Agriculture forever.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The current research is based upon the following objectives

- ✦ The developments and challenges of commercialization of agricultural commodities.
- ✦ To assess the problems faced by the direct sales by farmers during the lock down.
- ✦ The direct impact upon the sales of agricultural commodity and the Economy.
- ✦ To measure the reduce the demand for the Agricultural commodity during the lock down.
- ✦ To find out the government's role to promote the agricultural activity either satisfy or not.

METHODOLOGY:

- ✦ The study period covers only for the period of March 22nd onwards to forthcoming May 03rd, 2020, that is two phases of lockdown in India.
- ✦ The present study only consists of agriculture and its allied sectors.
- ✦ The government is likely to extend support at levels in the field of agricultural operations through modernized mechanisms.
- ✦ The Government should increase the storage capacity for agricultural produce, it would be used this kind of emergency that is COVID-19 lockdown. It will lead to all the farmers can enable to get a fair price for their produce.
- ✦ Presently, agricultural operations are taken by the migrant labour force also. In the northern part of India, the majority of the agricultural operations are taken by the migrant labour force. Here, we would try to create an environment for all sections of literate and illiterate peoples will hold the Agribusiness is more profit-oriented one.
- ✦ India is the second-largest arable land in the world, out of which amount of land, India would produce only 16% of GDP, whereas the 40 Percent of workers engaged with regard to this, our government must take appropriate policy measures to reduce the gap between GDP from Agriculture and its labour ratio.

- ✚ India's 30 per cent of the barren lands and wetlands can be modified into the cultivable lands for the increase of net shown area.
- ✚ Finally, Rivers are interconnecting as the main agenda for the development of the Indian agriculture sector.

1. GOVERNMENT IS LIKELY TO EXTENDED SUPORT AT ALL LEVELS IN THE FIELD OF AGRICULTURAL OPERATIONS THROUGH MODERNIZED MECHANISMS.

The government extended its support and recommends a standard operating procedure for farm operations. According to the government suggested standard operating procedures (SOP) for farm activities to deflect the threat of COVID-19. According to the new SOP, farmers to keep up social separating, individual cleanliness, and use machineries to limit labour requirement.

Land must be prepared by tractor-operated machinery, which requires minimal labor. Farmers should use seed and fertilizer drill for the preparation, which includes fewer workers, and this plan seeks to implement the upcoming Kharif season.

2. FARMERS SELL DIRECTLY DURING LOCKDOWN TO GET REASONABLE PRICE FOR THE PRODUCE

The central government has educated the states to allow farmers to sell their produce truly to clients during the lockdown time allotment to ensure their compensation isn't impacted by the limitations of the APMC Act. And this will help the farmers in selling their own produce things with the help of organization (FPO) farmer producer organisations and their cooperatives.

So far just Tamil Nadu and Karnataka have consented to unwind APMC Act during the lockdown and permit farmers to sell straightforwardly with no delegate. This mandi premises and permit farmers and cooperatives to sell produce from anyplace in the state without the prerequisite of any permit or any legal authorization.

And furthermore, the government has presented a few modules in its electronic mandi - eNAM to empower the immediate promoting of produce through farmer's gatherings group and cooperatives. This app will help the farmers to get the fair price for their produce without

middleman, and the government permitted to utilize government-owned distribution centers the status of mandi so exchanges can happen straightforwardly from there.

3. GENERATE EQUAL OPPORTUNITY TO ALL LEVEL PEOPLE IN AGRICULTURE

In general, Agricultural operations are handling by the poor farmers and middle-class farmers, it is a common feature almost in all parts of India. If it is agricultural work is fruit full and benefited large sections of the labour force the union and state government provide constant support to agriculture and increase the double the income of the farmers, it will attract to those who are undertaking the agriculture work. In this regard, in the school education and higher education department should also framework the agriculture Economy subject is compulsory one to from VI th standard up to degree class level. This kind of Education definitely motivates to the younger generations to catch the agricultural work is income generated profession forever.

4. POLICY MEASURES TO INCREASE THE GDP GAP LEVEL FROM AGRICULTURE

The large majority of the developed countries agriculture growth rate is 3 percent to 5 percent, Whereas in Indian Agriculture sector in the first five-year plan 1951-1956 the 60 per cent of income derived from the Agriculture sector, engaged by the 90 per cent of the labour force, As of now, it is shrinking together, only 16 per cent of National income obtained from the Agriculture sector and engaged by 40 per cent of the labour force.

In order to overcome this problem gradually, we should increase the ration of GDP from Indian Agriculture from 16 per cent to 30 per cent in the field of the agriculture sector as in turn, India's export of Agriculture share is fivefold increasing and it improves the foreign exchange reserves from Agriculture sector.

5.BARREN LAND DEVELOPMENT WILL IMPROVE AGRICULTURAL ECONOMY

The total agricultural land of India the 30 percent consists of barren lands. We should improve the barren lands converted into pucca arable land, that is most suitable for cultivation. Thereafter we can increase the net sown area of India's Agriculture sector, If we do that the productivity of the land also increases and also maintain the Environmental safeguard for the land as well as green pastures with everywhere in the region as well as the sufficient amount of food grains and pulses. Thus, the enormous number of benefits from barren lands move into the good arable lands in the arena of the agricultural Economy.

6.INTERCONNECTION OF RIVERS WILL DEVELOP INDIAN AGRICULTURAL SECTOR

Water is an essential input into agriculture in almost all its elements having a determining impact at the eventual yield. India is one of the few nations within the international gifted with substantial water resources. Being a monsoon we of the land frequently witnesses erratic rainfall causing massive harm to the social, financial, ecological and political material of the state.

Interlinking of rivers (ILR) programme as the main program for the improvement of the Indian agriculture area, in this programme, will link 60 rivers of India, along with river Ganga. Optimistically, with the assist of this ILR, there could be a reduction in the dependence of farmers on uncertain monsoon rains and there may also be hundreds of thousands of cultivated lands for irrigation.

The ILR programme objectives are to change over river water from the surplus areas to shortage areas within the country. It is the concept and prescient are to ensure more equity in the distribution of water by enhancing the provision of water in drought-susceptible and rainfed states. The ILR aims to supply one seventy-three billion cubic meters of river water via a Twelve thousand five hundred km of canal network to irrigate 34 million hectares.

The National Water Development Agency (NWDA) In 2005, is incorporated inter-state rivers into a one-third part of the NPP. So far, NWDA has received Forty-six proposals of interconnections from Nine states. Gujarat, Rajasthan, Maharashtra, Jharkhand, Chhattisgarh, Bihar, Tamil Nadu, Orissa, and Karnataka.

The successful completion of the programme we'll ready to produce around 450 million tons of food grains once a year to cater to the nutrition requirements of over 1.5 billion in 2050. to satisfy this challenge, irrigation potential should be expanded to 160 million hectares. it'll not be

possible without the interlinking of rivers. If interlinking of rivers is carried out with the aid of connecting thru canals, then such uneven water goes with the flow in one-of-a-kind river basins will get balanced.

The benefits of ILR, as per an estimate, around 12% (40 million hectares) of land in India are inclined to floods and around 68% of India's whole location is susceptible to drought. The interlinking of rivers programme is predicted to create a 35 million hectares irrigation facility in water-scarce western and peninsular regions. The more irrigation services that can be discovered for the duration of the will make positive engaging in the government's goal of doubling farm earnings in 2022 thru greater appropriate production and productivity.

The ILR will supply an enhanced to allied sectors of agriculture main to beneficial properties in employment, export revenue, and social and economic infrastructure growth. The profitable completion of the programme will ease the stress on groundwater assets and lead to the sustainable increase of water-deficit areas. For instance, interlinking of Godavari and Krishna rivers in Andhra Pradesh will lead to higher irrigation facilities that can be found throughout the in the Rayalaseema, which is one of the most backward areas in the country. Interlinking of rivers is, in reality, a good solution for the shortage of water.

Interlinking of rivers would be most recommended to the agriculture field due to the fact in India occupation of Huge manpower is as similar to businessman more are involved in the agriculture field as a farmer. Agriculture is every other important vicinity that will get a high-quality impact. The cultivated crops ought to get sufficient water provision round the year. This is going to be an extraordinarily greater boom of the Indian economy/agricultural increase of India.

7.LOCKDOWN IMPACTS -GOVERNMENT EXTENDED THEIR SUPPORT TO AGRICULTURAL OPERATION AND THE SUPPLY CHAIN

India has taken initial steps to curb the spread of COVID-19, ordering a 21-day nationwide lockdown of more than 1.2 billion people since March 22. The complete abolition of all economic activities, except essential services, is causing the economic crisis and distress for the

poor, increasing job losses and food insecurity. Without a regular salary or income, these agricultural, migrant and other informal workers will be severely affected during the lockdown.

Here, focus on the impacts on agriculture, distribution, food, and incomes.

COVID-19 disrupts certain activities in agriculture and related supply chains. Preliminary reports show that the lack of migrant workers is hampering some harvest operations, especially wheat and pulses in northwestern India. There is a very high level of interruptions in agricultural supply chains due to transportation issues and other issues. Prices for wheat, vegetables, and other crops have dropped, however, consumers often pay higher fees.

Below are some measures are needed to maintain the agricultural sector and supply chains operating smoothly.

I. Maintaining supply chains operating well is crucial to food security. Lack of food disruptions will cause death, make sure there is no lack of food distribution.

II. Farmers should continue to have access to markets. Without any interference from government officials. It may be a combination of private markets and government procurement.

III. Such as lockdown activities have increased, so has the need to supply groceries and e-commerce at home. This tendency should be encouraged and endorsed by the government.

IV. Agricultural peoples should be protected from the virus to the extent possible through testing and practicing social isolation. This will protect the agricultural sector people.

V. Lockdown guidelines have correctly issued by the government that exempt supply chain and farm operations. But we need to fix implementation issues that lead to labor shortages and falling prices should take immediate action to rectify.

VI. The most appropriate way to address this urgent need is to use social security nets to ease their lives with food and money.

VII. Farmers and agricultural workers must be included in government subsidies and social security programs that address the crisis.

VIII. The government should avoid export bans and import limitations to the maximum it will help to improve in these situations.

The government has promptly responded to the crisis and announced a relief package for the people affected by the lockdown, which includes food and money transfers. It serves millions of people working in agriculture and other sectors and many state governments have announced their own support packages.

8.FOOD SCARCITY BLOCKS FOOD SUPPLY CHAINS DUE TO TRANSPORT INTERRUPTION

After the government announced the results of the shutdown. Transport services are being shut down; India is likely to face a food crisis due to the lockdown triggered by the coronavirus. When it comes down to food availability, the nation has enough stock.

However, the availability of food plates can turn out to be a problem, as the gradually more disturbing supply chain, the Agricultural Produce Market Committee (APMC) has shut down Mandis, and the interstate movement of goods is restricted.

The extent to which of the anguish the country must feel depends on how quickly and how efficiently the connections between the field and the table are restored.

9.DURING LOCKDOWN: NECESSARY STEPS REQUIRED FOR CONTINUOUS MOVEMENT OF ESSENTIAL COMMODITIES

Lockdown period worst-hit food items are the problem will be with fruits and vegetables and at various levels, this report in The Indian Express noted, Regarding farm commodity traffic, interstate restrictions on indiscriminately imposed Inter-state truck restrictions will be affected when the crop is harvested. Later the harvested items must be packaged and shipped to the markets, which again requires workers, the driver, and free movement.

The product and its buyers are often in different states. Bihar getting its produce, rice from West Bengal, pulses from Katni and Satna in Madhya Pradesh, and mustard oil from Rajasthan. But with state borders sealed, it is unclear how smooth this transport traffic will be. The government has exempted good traffic from the lockdown, but how it operates at the highway level or at the local police station is another matter entirely.

The difference between essential and non-essential items has been eliminated, and "all goods" are allowed, but the possibility of being checked and harassed at every checkpoint is likely to exclude truck drivers and transportation, business owners.

10.SUPPLY CHAIN TO BE RUN WITHOUT ANY DISTURBANCE TO AVOID FOOD SCARCITY

The distribution wants urgent lubrication in the form of clear orders from the central and state governments that agricultural workers will not be harassed, and the movement of produce bearing vehicles will not be blocked at the state limits.

I. The statewide orders for the operations of the grocery, fruit and vegetable retailers will help.

II. The passenger rail service is halted, and the railway service can be pressed to carry farm produce.

III. Farmers can be given day or hourly slots with clear guarantees that their produce will be sold.

IV. The issue so far is not food it is people getting food. Urgent government intervention can fix that.

The above mention items are followed will avoid the supply chain disturbance totally.

REVIEW WITH REGARD TO LOCK DOWN IN INDIA

REVIEW 1:

COVID -19 LOCKDOWN - LABOUR CRISIS DEMAND DEVASTATE FARM SECTOR

Jonathan Ananda describes the farmer can meet the challenge of whether to laugh or cry at the time of lockdown in Maharashtra and Madhya Pradesh, with regard to the scarce labour force.

Shivdas Patil, a chilli farmer within the state's Jalgaon district, hoped that the rain would continue in Maharashtra till January this year. By the end of May, when the harvest is over, he's going to laugh until the bank. In normal years, rainfall rarely passes through December and the yield of chilli is 15-20 quintals per acre. He expects a bumper crop with plenty of rain this year, yielding more than 25 quintals per acre.

However, Patil doesn't realize whether to laugh or cry. That is on the grounds that it is just mid-April and harvesting is yet to peak, however, the lockdown has caused the lack of transportation of his produce and not many buyers at mandis. We carry our products to the market, but there are no buyers to purchase. A day or two ago I sold four quintals of Chilli at Rs 10 for each kg. On better occasions I sell at Rs 30-40 for every kg," Patil said. In this way lockdown period legitimately influences the Marketing cost of the chilli in Maharashtra.

Pushkar Banakar Point out the problem of Wheat grower in Madhya Pradesh

Wheat farmer Shyam Dwivedi, in Madhya Pradesh's Umaria district, too believes a bumper harvest. Grain growers like Dwivedi, who own large areas of land, are confronted with another issue: the scarcity of agricultural labourers. Dwivedi owns 40 acres of land and requires a minimum 50 workers to harvest wheat. But as most agricultural labourers have moved to their native places in Bihar and eastern UP, he faces the risk of crop loss.

The Shortage of labour delays the harvesting, which we needed to finish by April 15 2020. Even those labourers who are readily available remain demanding up to Rs 300 on a daily basis, and that is double the usual daily wage, Dwivedi stated. Rural India is in trouble due to being locked lockdown from Kerala to Punjab, Odisha and Maharashtra, threatened to deal physical setback to the farm and its related sector,

There are no official statistics on the number of migrant agricultural labourers falls into the informal sector, however as per the International Labour Organization's assessments, which depends on Census 2011 records, near twenty-four lakh migrants labour in fields across India.

REVIEW -2

LOCKDOWN DISASTEROUS FOR THE AGRARIAN ECONOMY

The Editorial of Times of India to assess the agricultural occupation during the period of COVID-19 lockdown in India.

The consequent lockdown in India couldn't have been more awful for the agrarian economy. April to June covers a period when the country's economy spins around the collection of winter grains, for example, wheat and maize. This is likewise a period when the harvest cycle covers potatoes and onions, and groundwork for the Kharif season starts.

All those measures are labor-intensive and contradict the policy of social isolation with the requirements of an important agricultural season. The good news is that there is still time to change the social distance to meet public health and agricultural needs. Moreover, adjusting the logistics chain will help prevent the rise in prices of fruits and vegetables, which account for nearly 25% of India's agricultural output.

Therefore, the next stage of social distance is to quantify the role that agriculture plays in the revival of the economy. To overcome this problem, district administrations facilitate direct access between farmers and urban consumers during the lockdown, narrowing the layers of agents.

This should now be standardized to decrease the stranglehold Agricultural Produce Market Committees have on intermediation. Rivalry functions admirably all over. It's likewise time to change land renting enactment to give farmers more alternatives. In many cases, agriculture is viewed as a delay in the rest of the economy. This time, it very well may be in the vanguard of revival.

REVIEW -3

SCARCITY OF LABOUR DELAYS THE CROP HARVEST

Farhan Hamed, labour contractor based in Bahraich district said. The labor shortage also affects farms in UP, which supply large quantities of farmhands to Punjab and Haryana. In addition to the threat of illness, fear of isolation is playing a major role in the minds of workers who are not ready to leave their villages.

Despite losing their jobs, most workers are determined to stay in their villages and live their lives under a government welfare scheme, which has expanded their network since the epidemic outbreak, Hamed said. In the absence of sufficient labour, farmers are drilling for harvesting machines. There is a serious shortage of integrated harvesters, as the number of machines bought from other states has declined due to the lockdown, this can interfere with procurement activities that require labor for loading, cleaning, and packaging.

There are only permanent workers and there is no possibility of workers returning in the current procurement season. Wages are already rising. There will be a struggle for available labor in this situation, with wages rising from Rs.400-500 to Rs.600-700, Garg said

Most farmers have difficulty planting crops. There is a 50 percent labour scarcity. If lockdown remains, farmers are worried about planting crops for the coming season. Agricultural Advisory Council, in Madhya Pradesh. Informed planting fruits and vegetables would also be affected.

Experts said government welfare measures could keep workers in their villages. Agriculture will suffer from a shortage of labor in the short term. The severe shortage of labour poses a serious challenge to crop procurement and threatens to have a lasting impact on agriculture, as it will delay the harvesting of winter-sown crops, especially wheat, and delay the planting of the next crop.

REVIEW -4

COVID 19 LOCKDOWN HURDLES TRANSPORT AND LABOUR SCARCITY HITS AGRICULTURAL TRADER'S LIVELIHOOD

The Current circumstance of lockdown Traders state this will crash farmers as their products will start rotting, while urban consumers will face high-level price except if the authorities take urgent steps. Police officials say it is difficult to determine whether a person or an empty commercial vehicle is involved in the trading of essential goods.

The supply of fruits and vegetables can drop drastically in a day Traffic barrier and labor scarcity have halted operations amid fears of COVID-19 lockdown. Fear has hampered operations, prompting many traders to halt operations, although Mandis ruins properly open under government pressure. The current circumstance will destroy farmers as their produce will begin decaying, while urban shoppers will confront high as- can- be costs except if the authorities make dire strides.

Mandis, they were now facing a disturbance in the trade as trucks are unable to move in the lockdown. The fruit trade in Mandi has been halted as farmers face difficulties in shipping their produce, at the same time it is also difficult to dispatch.

Because of lockdown restriction, the police beat the customers who came to the market. If they don't allow customers to market, we need to reduce buying from growing areas. Farmers want the government to issue passes to buyers who want to come to mandis said by the farmers.

In this lockdown transportation is a huge bottleneck, most of the trucks are stuck in the state border crossing, with the drivers running out of money to sustain

For smooth traffic, the police department has been instructed, and the trucks will be holding stickers, that they are taking essential goods, most of the traders in Azadpur Mandi are decided to stop the operations. In addition, many villages are not permitting people to go to towns to work, be afraid they will bring back the feared coronavirus and traders at the mandi stop their operations as they are afraid of contacting COVID-19.

REVIEW -5

LOCKDOWN BRINGS DOWN TRADERS AND AGRICULTURE BUSINESS

GODSON WISELY DASS finds out the middlemen are playing the pivotal role in reducing the price of the chilli farmers in Toothkudi, Tamil Nadu, during the period of lockdown.

In Toothkudi district, chilli is cultivated on 27,400 acres in the rain-fed tracks of vilathikulam pudhur, kovil patti and ettayapurram here and the chief varieties are samba (long) and Mundur (short). After the harvest, chilli should be sun-dried for three days.

Shekar, a chilli farmer from P Meenatanipuram near vilathikulam said Quintal of re-chilli was usually purchased for Rs.14,000 to 15,000 However, this year traders quoted Rs,8,000 to 9,000, claiming that there was no demand.

Also, the yield dropped this year, due to heavy rain during flowing season, to three quintals an acre as against four quintals, he said.

Farmers said red-chilli never cost below Rs 14,000 a quintal before. They said the traders are milking the unusual circumstances to make hay. They said they would not be able to even pay wages to farmlands if they sold the produce Rs.9,000 a quintal.

When contacted, a senior official from Agriculture Business and Marketing Department said traders might be quoting the procurement price low because of restricted traffic due to lockdown.

He, however, appealed to farmers to not sell their produce at lower prices but instead store them at government-regulated markets functioning in pudhur vilathikulam blocks at Zero rent for a month.

The farmers demand adequate procurement price for their chilli produce and a rent-free self-regulated market for their production of chilli.

CASE STUDIES WITH REGARD TO LOCK DOWN- MYRIAD PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED BY AGRICULTURAL FARMERS AND THEIR PRODUCE

CASE STUDY -1

N. Ramesh, Correspondent of the New Indian Express, find out the farmers in Tamil Nadu bear the brunt of this present lockdown.

In many locations in Trichy and Thanjavur, farmers are leaving their banana bunches to grow in the trees because they could not be removed were unable to transport their bananas because of locked down.

From these places, bananas are taken to Kerala to make chips. Before the restrictions were lifted, our bananas were already ripe, but Kerala will not accept them. Due to this, 20 percent of the banana produced in Trichy is now worthless, said the farmer chief Aylai Sivasuriyan.

The one-week break between restrictions and raising them is a blow to banana growers, Throughout Tiruchy about 15,000 acres and 11,500 acres of banana are cultivated in Trichy and Thanjavur districts.

Farmers are now worried that bananas prices have fallen rapidly due to lack of demand in the markets of other states as auction houses are not functioning.

Farmers will earn revenue from selling banana leaves to restaurants. Farmers sell the leaves to agents, who usually send bundles every day to restaurants in distant places, including Chennai, these banana leaves will be sent through omnibuses every day. Farmers in the Tirukkattupalli area said the demand for banana leaves fell due to the closure of most restaurants across the state and the lack of bus services. Farmers pay Rs. 1 lakh per annum for selling banana leaves. Now,

that opportunity is also closed. In another case of commodities like groundnut, Onion, and cotton are unable to marketing in on timely manner.

Around 8,000 hectares of cultivated groundnut in the Thanjavur district has been partially affected, as farmers are unable to hire workers because of low prices. I planted onions on five acres and harvested 20 tons. But I could only sell half of it, and the rest is stored in my house. Before lockdown, traders usually take onions from our village and it will be shipped to Chennai every day. Nowadays, they come every three days. Another concern is the high costs of renting a vehicle.

CASE STUDY -2

The Times of India News Network points out the poor purchasing prices of the farming products during the lockdown it affects the life of the farmers. Theni district farmers in Cumbum valley raised vegetables for Kerala Vishu festivals, unfortunately, state borders are closed due to lockdown, this affects the farmer's produce product.

The rate supplied for the region's famed bananas and grapes, prepared for harvest, may additionally no longer even assist get better the cost, farmers lament.

Mr. Raveendran of Kamaya Koundan Patti close to Cumbum, who had grown beetroot in six acres, stated there are neither consumers nor labour to harvest. An 80kg bag of beetroot, which used to fetch 700-800 round this time of the year, is going for much less than 300 now. "Unless we get 350, we will now not get better our fee even," stated Raveendran.

The harvest covers approximately 400 acres throughout the Cumbum area. Just About 30 percent of the banana cultivated in Cumbum valley is being exported. One More 30 percent will go to Kerala as well as the to Madurai, Chennai, and Bengaluru. Remaining to the non-availability of workers and transport and work stoppage of exports, the sector is severely hit. We're trying to sell produce products at a very low price to recover at least twenty percent of the crop. The rest could decompose in the fields itself, stated Natraj Kumar, a banana farmer.

The other significant incidents regarding the no buyers in the other parts of Tamilnadu.

A farmer near Pollachi, **J. Balakrishnan** from Vettaikaranputhur says about 450 acres of banana farms would have to suffer as the yield is getting overripened due to the fact of no takers.

A banana farmer Namakkal district **M. Rajendran**, in Mohanur has stated that there are currently no takers for bananas at even 50 per bunch.

Naidupuram farmer **Madasamy** in Kodaikanal is using to sell carrot at 40 per kg prior to the lockdown started. He is now struggling to sell the produce items at Rs 18 per kg now. But those who purchase from him are selling in Madurai the retail trade at 60 per kg, he said.

In Thalavadi Erode district farmer **Prasad Narayanan** has stated that following all expenditure, a farmer gets just 2 per kg of tomatoes, but traders making a profit of 25 per kg in some locations.

S Chinnaraj of Manachanallur in Trichy district stated traders attempt to pull down the costs mentioning transportation problems. Denkanikottai farmers are selling forty-five kg potato bags at 600 when the retail value of the produce is 45 per kg.

Therefore, no single farmers are earned enough normal profits at that point in time of lockdown.

CASE STUDY -3

LOCK DOWN HITS TAMIL NADU FARM WORKERS DAY-TO-DAY FARMING WORK AND FARMERS CULTIVATION

N. Ramesh and Antony Fenando, Correspondent of the New Indian Express, find out the farmers in Tamil Nadu has taken hit due to lack of farmworkers.

After the lockdown, farmworkers in accordance with the Mahatma Gandhi Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) in the delta region have been the worst hit. According to some sources, over 40,000 workers have been engaged in the works under the scheme until such time lockdown announced, when the shutdown came into effect. The works were not taken up. This came at the moment when the samba cultivation was over and there was absolutely no work in the fields. Throughout this period, normally, more farmworkers looking for work under MGNREGA for their living.

A farmworker **C Ganapathy (58)**, from Thekkur near Orathanadu, a work card-holder in accordance with the MGNREGA, stated that his family is sustaining with the whole grain purchased from the fair price store. We actually don't know what to do later because there is no work or in accordance with the MGNREGA or in the fields, he told.

R Natarajan, a farmer, from Iluppur near Kilvelur in Nagapattinam and delta districts the cultivation and the crop of pulses by the year has taken a hit due to the lack of farmworkers. Sources stated over 2,20,000 hectares in delta districts plus 80,000 hectares in Nagapattinam have been affected by the shortage of farmworkers. We're neither getting harvesters and neither the workers because of restriction, stated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Presently India has a 136-crore population. The agriculture sector only provides the entire satisfaction of demand for food articles. During this COVID-19 lock down the union and state government slowly relaxation of norms and support measures for the Agriculture sector. The agricultural and its allied activities like Horticultural, flower cultivation, vegetable cultivation fruit marketing, Agricultural marketing transport are exempted from the lockdown restrictions. Agricultural crop loans are extended by the moratorium period for 3 months. The easy functioning of Agricultural advertising services, the digitally linked e-nam market gadget used to be touted alongside with a logistics module connecting farmers and traders to a community of nearly 8 lakh trucks and 2 lakh transporters. Perishable products moved through railways around sixty-seven routes introduced. An Agricultural transport call center used to be set up to cope with transport issues.

Flow ever, the majority of the farmers and advertising and marketing of transport offerings severely confronted undesirable things to do by means of the police personnel and the state govt officials. Totally, regulations and policies were imposed by the not in uniform throughout India.

In May parts of India, the central government instructions issued against by the COVID-19. The government's instructions have not percolated down to district magistrates and super indent of Police resulting in the harassment of farmers and agricultural traders and supply-chain disruptions says the farmer. Agriculture secretary Siras Hussain, who is now a fellow at Indian Council for Research on International Economic relations New Delhi. Nationally we must recognise that the implications of COVID-19 go beyond health issues.

Presently, in several parts of the country in which the rabi harvest season has already come to a nearer one, sowing of the Kharif or summertime season crop has already begun. In fact, authorities' statistics exhibit early displaying of paddy with the sown region nearly forty percent

greater than standard by means of April 10, 2020. The Indian Metrological Department (IMD) forecast of a normal monsoon has bolstered the Agriculture Ministry to target an all-time record production of food grain of 298.3 million tonnes in 2020-21.

The lockdown has proven that agriculture is reliably the backbone of the Indian Economy, Coronavirus or no longer farm production drives on due to the fact the demand for ingredients will normally there. And so prolonged as we encounter our Kharif and rabi the production target, we are glad, says Sharma Although the handy for an extra cost to the farmer to farming workers, it is no longer taken into account in that system.

He pointed out the tragic snapshots of lakhs of migrant people trudging returned to their villages due to the lockdown. This reverse migration proves they have been in reality agricultural refugees, who left for the cities solely due to the fact they should no longer make a dwelling in the fields, he stated “Everyone is speaking about the want to make investments in public health as soon as the COVID-19 disaster is over. our farmers and agricultural people are additionally frontline people in the course of this time and they additionally deserve greater interest closer to growing the productiveness of the agriculture sector. If we can make investments in agriculture and from above it so it is profitable, then we will have without a doubt discovered something from this crisis.

Finally, the Indian Agriculture zone is free from the authority’s orders and restrictions, on every occasion a disaster arises or not. This sector offers are an ample no of scope for whole our rural loads and employment possibility wholesale merchants to retail traders. If it is a growing field of agriculture, simultaneously we can reap the benefits of water conservation and improve the water levels both in rural and urban areas.

All over the world, the developed countries are mainly concentrated more on the Industrial sector but show less interest in agriculture work. As the consequences of the duration of COVID-19, the majority of the developed countries people are from the long queue for getting their food by sitting inside the car. Whereas in the Indian case, where is no source in the food level. Poor and middle-class peoples get rice from the public distribution system and also, they have financial assistance from the govt by the relief packages of COVID-19.

The vegetable and fruits vendors frustrated by the police personnel by the middle of the lockdown, even though, the supply chain of the Agricultural commodities is successfully distributed and full fill the wants of 136 corers of people of our nation. Till now, the success mantra behind the Indian Economy scenario the productivity of the agricultural sector, whenever unforeseen occurrences happened. Thus, the Agriculture sector proves the development, without agriculture.

CONCLUSION:

The dominant population of Agriculture labour force would improve the standard of India's Economy at the time of lockdown, We would like to maintain the present level of Agricultural development, we start a large shops of Agricultural machinery and the manufacturing distribution and sale of fertilizers pesticides and seeds with 100 percent subsidy manner.

In order to protect and reduce the wastage of Agricultural produce, cold storage facilities to set up in each village in rural India. The govt should take a keen interest on alleviating unemployment and underemployment in and unemployment in the Agriculture sector. The micro-level planning is implemented to mitigate the Acute shortage of labour force in the Indian Agriculture sector. Another point of the suggestion is MGNREGA workers can also utilize the farming activities in the part of Agriculture development.

Finally, our Indian Agriculture sector is re-oriented in the new ways, efficient ways, and modernized techniques would Definitely growing India's Agricultural Economy.

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